

China vs. the World

IQ as a Strategic Asset; a graphical comparison

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ABSTRACT

Intelligence Quotient is a reliable measure of problem and puzzle solving ability and rational skill sets. It has a strong correlation to the ability to control emotion and avoid violent conflict. But in terms of National Security, it is an asset in particular to engineering of solutions to societal problems, and other STEM issues and development. In other words, it is a practical measure of future growth, vis-a-vis population use, growth, and of pragmatic concerns of infrastructural development. Thinking on this issue, a nation's future is tied not only to capitalistic growth based on population, but more pointedly to the available IQ asset "at the ready" for that development. In this paper, the author demonstrates the predictable difficulties the US and allies such as Europe and India will have in competing directly (individually) with China in a global marketplace of ideas, products, development, and STEM. Looking at the comparisons, it is clear that the problem is worsened as IQ rarity is increased. Therefore, high IQ individuals in the allies will be a rare asset relative to their Chinese counterparts. The resultant of this investigation is that new solutions to leveraging this rarer IQ must be provided in order to offset the strategic disadvantage (anti-Shi 勢, deemed Que 缺). The author will attempt to provide a few simple examples, using martial arts concepts and Art of War principles. However, a unique project should be provided for engineering in more non-martial and non-business means.

Keywords: IQ - national security - China - United States - European Union - India - Russia

Introduction

Intelligence is not merely about gathering information: it is about application of that knowledge. Specifically we mean problem-solving, although a further IQ we could term “Wisdom Quotient”¹ might be an even more important measure when comparing ancient cultures (like China or India) to newer cultures (like the United States). Problem-solving is a nascent or innate need for STEM fields² and it is the primary concern of IQ testing, which relies on logical puzzles to determine a score. Most IQ systems are based upon a 200 max score scale, which is what we are concerned with here.

China’s average IQ is 105, while the US, Europe, and India are all lower (98, 100, and 82 respectively). This could and should be considered a strategic disadvantage (que), in the same way that a short man is disadvantaged in basketball, or a thin man in weight lifting, or an obese man in swimming. There is nothing odd about this kind of discussion, whatever feelings it elicits. In a purely rational discourse, we are simply comparing relative abilities to problem solve and engineer solutions. In an era of increased cyber attacks, this is a matter of national security and state sovereignty.³

However, based upon the illegal (often wanton) actions of China in covering up the COVID “gain-of-function” research⁴, lab leak⁵, and deadliness of SARS-Cov-2⁶, the world is awakening to a larger concern. Just as the world was slow to wake up to Hitler’s National Socialist party, it seems slow to realize that China’s ‘beneficence’ (such as the now-known spy network⁷ of Confucius Institutes⁸, or the “Road and Belt Initiative”⁹) is actually colonialism¹⁰ and imperialism¹¹ masked under the guise of economic trade¹². According to Dr. Pillsbury¹³ and retired Air Force General Robert Spalding¹⁴ (both favored insiders of the CCP at one time), the view of the CCP about America’s post World War II boom is warped not to view the Marshall Plan¹⁵ as a form of altruism, but the acts of the new Ba 霸 hegemon.

In point of fact, the CCP has considered freedom and democracy as direct threats to its own “100 year marathon” plans to dominate the world, replacing first the USSR, then the United States and NATO. Therefore it literally declared an official war upon the Declaration of Independence, and the Bill of Rights¹⁶. Since Xi Jinping’s rise to dominance, and the flushing of millions of Communist Party opposition members¹⁷, he has crushed Hong Kong’s freedoms¹⁸, ending its status as the #2 freest state on Earth¹⁹, and has made frightening speeches, such as the following at the 100 year anniversary of the CCP celebration:

¹ [https://mbassous.wordpress.com/category/wisdom-quotient/#:~:text=Wisdom%20Quotient%20\(WQ\)%20is%20the,and%20manage%20the%20implications%20positively.](https://mbassous.wordpress.com/category/wisdom-quotient/#:~:text=Wisdom%20Quotient%20(WQ)%20is%20the,and%20manage%20the%20implications%20positively.)

² Science, technology, engineering, and medicine.

³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ya7WFsIsD9Q>

⁴ <https://nypost.com/2021/07/20/fauci-sen-paul-clash-over-gain-of-function-research-at-wuhan-lab-in-china/>

⁵ <https://www.nytimes.com/2021/06/20/science/covid-lab-leak-wuhan.html>

⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/COVID-19_misinformation_by_China

⁷ <https://freebeacon.com/national-security/chinas-spy-network-united-states-includes-25000-intelligence-officers/>

⁸ Aside from spying on Congressmen, the Confucius Institute contracts filed with universities are often full of redacted and blacked out information, even with a full “Public Records” request. The following is the contract signed with the University of Kentucky - the author’s alma mater - and as one can see it is heavily redacted. <https://bit.ly/3BhuWT5>

⁹ <https://www.cfr.org/belt-and-road-initiative>

¹⁰ <https://www.leedsfinsights.com/post/neo-colonialism-in-africa-the-chinese-belt-and-road-initiative>

¹¹ <https://www.lowyinstitute.org/the-interpretor/belt-and-road-colonialism-chinese-characteristics>

¹² <https://citizentruth.org/china-africa-belt-and-road-initiative/>

¹³ “100 Year Marathon,” Dr. Pillsbury, 2014

¹⁴ “Stealth War: How China Took Over While America’s Elite Slept,” R. Spalding, 2018 <https://www.stealth-war.org/>

¹⁵ <https://www.britannica.com/event/Marshall-Plan>

¹⁶ See the above books. Also <https://www.washingtontimes.com/news/2017/jan/27/us-impending-war-china/>

¹⁷ <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/world/china/xi-jinping-undertakes-fresh-round-of-brutal-purge-in-china/articleshow/77943864.cms>

¹⁸ <https://nypost.com/2020/05/21/chinas-sudden-rush-to-crush-hong-kongs-freedom/>

¹⁹ <https://www.heritage.org/index/ranking>

“The Chinese people will never allow foreign forces to bully, oppress or enslave us. Whoever nurses delusions of doing that will crack their heads and spill blood on the Great Wall of steel built from the flesh and blood of 1.4 billion Chinese people.”²⁰

The irony of this speech is, of course as despots are wont to do, a complete fabrication and coverup for internal atrocities²¹, tyranny, and megalomania. As socialists²² typically do, he is foisting upon others what he himself is doing²³ and engaging in “The Big Lie”²⁴. It is a similar problem as per Black Lives Matter (corporation)²⁵ ²⁶, antifa (terrorist organization²⁷), and the Sunrise Movement²⁸ and Democratic Socialists of America²⁹ (organizations behind these, and funded by George Soros). They stage false flags and leave bricks and other weaponry in place³⁰, and then blame the opposition³¹. The media then covers through a form of gaslighting and video and audio manipulation³², knowing they will never be forced to retract or pay for all lies and mistakes (nor in time), though they repeatedly lose lawsuits³³. There is a strong suspicion of direct and indirect funding³⁴ of these movements from the CCP, who employs a literal “50 cent army”³⁵ to help shape western opinions on the internet³⁶, and uses other forms of asymmetric warfare³⁷ in order to engage in “Unrestricted”³⁸ (or Total³⁹) war with the United States and NATO allies, and to dominate colonial targets in

²⁰ <https://www.businessinsider.com/xi-countries-opposing-china-crack-heads-spill-blood-2021-7>

²¹ <https://www.voanews.com/east-asia-pacific/china-slams-g-7-statement-criticizing-human-rights-record>

²² <https://www.forbes.com/sites/rainerzitelmann/2020/03/16/socialism-the-failed-idea-that-never-dies/>

²³ <https://www.northeastshooters.com/xen/threads/why-do-socialists-always-blame-someone-else.3480/>

²⁴ There is an infamous case of lying among American socialists, on purpose on TV. However, the search results are not candid. The author did find this example, in a rare case of journalism from CNN (pre 2020):

<https://www.cnn.com/2019/11/09/europe/berlin-wall-30-years-schools-grm-intl/index.html>

²⁵ <https://blacklivesmatter.com/about/>

²⁶ <https://www.dailysignal.com/2020/07/07/these-18-corporations-gave-money-to-black-lives-matter-group/>

²⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Big_Lie

²⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DgsnyHILdb8>

²⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=S7v3G3kdTYM>

³⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zFYnbLtySus>

³¹ They come so primed to fight, that the “Proud Boys” organization was able to set them up against themselves, and “pull the chair out” by not showing up. Antifa took to attacking itself. The Proud Boys are notoriously primed for violence, themselves, but their label as a White Supremacist organization is far overstated: their leader at the time of the Nov. 6 riots was a Mexican-American. They could, under some broad views, be considered also a terrorist organization, but they themselves have never set out as antifa or BLM to burn buildings or terrorize local civilians. Other, far more extreme nationalistic and far or alt-right organizations have, however. Unfortunately far left organizations like the Southern Poverty Law Center dilute the discussion by aggregating patriotic organizations and all militias, with such hate organizations! This is incredibly problematic since American Patriotism and American Nationalism are often at odds with one another. A subject for another paper.

³² <https://www.projectveritas.com/news/video-james-okeefe-breaks-down-big-win-against-the-new-york-times-in-veritas/>

³³ Aside from the Nick Sandmann incident, outlets such as the Washing Post, Huffington Post, and even the New York Times have repeatedly lied - outright - and caused a lot of damage to persons’ reputations. Later they pay for it, but the narrative is firmly planted (as propaganda) in the minds of their constituency.

³⁴

<https://www.datalounge.com/thread/20086703-project-veritas-and-their-undercover-sting-operation-against-the-washingto-n-post>

³⁵ <https://economicindependencefromchina.com/chinas-50-cent-army/>

³⁶ https://www.theepochtimes.com/revealing-the-operations-of-chinas-official-troll-army-system_3311813.html

³⁷ <https://www.ausa.org/sites/default/files/LWP-58-Defining-Asymmetric-Warfare.pdf>

³⁸ <https://www.oodalooop.com/documents/unrestricted.pdf>

³⁹ <https://www.cc.gatech.edu/~tpilsch/INTA4803TP/Articles/Total%20War-definition&discussion.pdf>

Africa^{40 41}, Australia^{42 43}, Oceania⁴⁴, India⁴⁵, Eastern Europe^{46 47 48}, South America⁴⁹, Cuba⁵⁰, Italy^{51 52} and Sri Lanka⁵³. Southeast Asia appears to be a region of particular thorniness to the CCP, and in its paranoia has been building fake islands^{54 55} and then claiming them as real islands belonging to China since ancient times⁵⁶. They also build out commercial ships into warships⁵⁷, and enter into neighbor's territorial waters (such as the Philippines⁵⁸).

All of this seems at first (and probably still does to the Chinese people themselves, who are generally patriotic and nationalistic⁵⁹), as defense mechanisms against United States' "aggression."⁶⁰ But actually since General MacArthur, the United States has been reluctant to flex its power in the region and has maintained only ambivalent interest in keeping a Pacific buffer zone⁶¹. If anything, the US approached China as an ally since Richard Nixon⁶² in order to use the CCP as a hedge against its former best friend, the Soviet Union (who had smartly realized the CCP's long term goals to replace Soviet Communism with its own particularly imperial and Qinshi-huangdi form of it⁶³). Chinese Communism is now famously pseudo-capitalistic⁶⁴, but it wasn't set free by the Communist party. It broke free because of the helpfulness of foolish, arrogant bureaucrats of the IMF, World Bank, and Federal Reserve Bank⁶⁵.

Where does this leave the world? When a "tiger grows its wings" (如虎添翼) as the Chinese saying goes, it is difficult to avoid bloodshed and terror. "When two tigers occupy the same mountain, one must be killed."⁶⁶ It's a tiger... flying about. In Chinese lore only a dragon can surpass such a fell beast. China has spent years "deceiving the sky"⁶⁷ (瞞天過海) and building "phantom cities"⁶⁸ in order to fool the world, and lay

⁴⁰ <https://www.panafricanalliance.com/china-africa-colonialism/>

⁴¹ <https://docs.house.gov/meetings/FA/FA16/20180307/106963/HHRG-115-FA16-Transcript-20180307.pdf>

⁴² <https://www.internationalaffairs.org.au/australianoutlook/abc-china-interference-investigations/>

⁴³ <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/articles/china/2018-03-09/how-china-interferes-australia>

⁴⁴ <https://thedi diplomat.com/2021/07/chinas-air-incursions-into-taiwans-adiz-focus-on-anti-access-and-maritime-deterrence/>

⁴⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2020_China%E2%80%93India_skirmishes

⁴⁶ <https://www.dw.com/en/chinas-new-silk-road-brings-great-promise-to-eastern-europe/a-36271021>

⁴⁷ <https://thedi diplomat.com/2018/08/the-belt-and-road-in-europe-5-years-later/>

⁴⁸ Dissenting opinion:

<https://pandapawdragonclaw.blog/2019/05/05/the-myth-of-the-belt-and-road-in-central-and-eastern-europe/>

⁴⁹ <https://jia.sipa.columbia.edu/online-articles/chinas-stakes-venezuela-are-too-high-be-ignored>

⁵⁰

https://www.uscc.gov/sites/default/files/Research/China%27s%20Engagement%20with%20Latin%20America%20and%20the%20Caribbean_.pdf

⁵¹ <https://foreignpolicy.com/2021/06/24/italy-china-policy-belt-road/>

⁵² <https://blogs.loc.gov/law/2020/05/italy-a-new-silk-road-between-italy-and-china-the-belt-and-road-initiative/>

⁵³ <https://thedi diplomat.com/2021/05/china-in-sri-lanka-the-colombo-port-conundrum/>

⁵⁴ <https://www.newsweek.com/china-south-china-sea-islands-build-military-territory-expand-575161>

⁵⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GLI8gZ3skmY>

⁵⁶ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZVn_7Yu5Fsw

⁵⁷ <https://thedi diplomat.com/2020/07/chinas-maritime-militia-vessels-may-be-military-objectives-during-armed-conflict/>

⁵⁸ <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2021/4/6/philippine-warns-china-of-unwanted-hostilities-over-sea-dispute>

⁵⁹ <https://news.harvard.edu/gazette/story/2020/07/long-term-survey-reveals-chinese-government-satisfaction/>

⁶⁰ Hard to say the United States has been aggressive since it had every opportunity (and reason) to invade China post World War 2, and Korea, and Vietnam wars, and did not.

⁶¹ <https://thedi diplomat.com/2015/08/when-the-us-and-china-were-allies/>

⁶² <https://www.historytoday.com/history-matters/richard-nixons-opening-china-and-closing-gold-window>

⁶³ <https://www.history.com/this-day-in-history/rupture-between-ussr-and-china-grows-worse>

⁶⁴ The black market and hidden economy, as well as 5 year plans, reduce the form of capitalism, and it does not have any form of a free market. The Chinese people have been capitalistic and innovative, however, far longer than the West.

⁶⁵ The lure of vast emerging markets and a population with savings proved too much, even for Cold War wisdom.

⁶⁶ 一山不容二虎,

<https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/%E4%B8%80%E5%B1%B1%E4%B8%8D%E5%AE%B9%E4%BA%8C%E8%99%8E>

⁶⁷ See B. Gertz's book. But the idiom means "Mask one's real goals from those in authority who lack vision by not alerting them to one's movements or any part of one's plan." https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Thirty-Six_Stratagems

⁶⁸ Literally "Ghost Cities" <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=le6zd3Rwu4c>

'friendly' traps (反客為主)⁶⁹. Now it is engaging in a mad rush to finish the job with its digital e-yuan⁷⁰, and making deals with the now eager Russian ascendancy, eager to reestablish itself and escape the tight grip of the West's financial throttling of its economy^{71 72}. Who can blame Russia?⁷³ They aren't foolish enough to fall for China's lies, and have been involved in meddling in Chinese and Japanese affairs of the region for over 200 years⁷⁴. Spy roads between the nations are now established ancient pipelines. But now they are also building literal pipelines⁷⁵. China wants, desperately, to be the world's reserve currency⁷⁶ and the center of all financial hegemony⁷⁷. It wants (indeed asserts its right) to be the Ba⁷⁸. The author maintains, based on this present analysis, that without following some of the suggestions of China's Art of War (bingfa 兵法) texts: **it will be**. This is, as the Chinese idiom says "as easy as a stone smashing an egg"⁷⁹ or "a boulder rolling downhill."

⁶⁹ Ibid. "Make the host and the guest exchange roles (反客為主, Fǎn kè wéi zhǔ): Usurp leadership in a situation where one is normally subordinate. Infiltrate one's target. Initially, pretend to be a guest to be accepted, but develop from inside and become the owner later."

⁷⁰ <https://www.investopedia.com/understanding-chinas-digital-yuan-5090699>

⁷¹ <https://home.treasury.gov/news/press-releases/jy0127>

⁷² <https://fas.org/sgp/crs/row/IF10779.pdf>

⁷³ The author is not a pro-Russia supporter, per se, however, if Germany got two 2nd chances, why hasn't Russia? It is no surprise that they've fallen backwards since 1991's major reforms, into a land of heavy handedness.

⁷⁴ <https://www.history.com/this-day-in-history/soviets-declare-war-on-japan-invade-manchuria>

⁷⁵ <https://www.newsweek.com/russia-china-gas-pipeline-first-bridge-1475067>

⁷⁶ <https://www.thebalance.com/yuan-reserve-currency-to-global-currency-3970465>

⁷⁷ <https://foreignpolicy.com/2020/08/21/dollar-global-reserve-currency-yuan-china/>

⁷⁸ See: Stealth War

⁷⁹ Technically 以卵击石 means for one to try to smash a stone with an egg, implying impossibility.

China vs. The United States, a study in a problem of IQ Que

The concept of shi is that, as its homophone (實 meaning excess) suggests, it is plenty of or at least trying to expand. But in the West we have Que: a shrinking⁸⁰, aging, overweight society⁸¹, hellbent on genocide of the unborn⁸² and a literal anti-fact dumbing down of society. It is “Atlas Shrugged” finally coming to life. It wasn’t a natural emergence, but bought and paid for by very rich capitalist-hegemony⁸³. They made their money, but do not believe in the American Dream or even the value of European economic sovereignty⁸⁴. The resulting agenda of Que was most obviously proven when Donald J. Trump won the 45th Presidency as a populist, and set about freeing the American economy, demanding the world pay for itself and applying tariffs, and was being impeached even before he took office⁸⁵. One could note COVID was an extremely coincidental event for the Democrats and other Deep State rivals⁸⁶, coming along as it did to shut down the world’s largest economy^{87 88} just as it was breaking China’s⁸⁹.

Nevertheless, actually President Trump was fighting an uphill battle, rather like Sisyphus. It was always likely to end in a failure for which the happy-go-plucky entrepreneur was going to be blamed for policies set up by his opponents over 40 years ago in the Senate. Why? Not because he particularly failed: he achieved by far the most of his promised agenda than any sitting President in living memory.⁹⁰ Rather, because the people themselves are easy to fool.

It isn’t in the purview of this paper to cover the costs of criminality, or to divide up the IQ distributions by race or make cases for the economic inequalities (or lack of productivity and drains on society, depending on the sociopolitical point of view) within the US economy and population. The entire population is treated herein as an aggregate. As there are substantial portions of the United States with lower IQs as an average, which also have higher rates of incarceration and unemployment⁹¹, it can be understood that this adds to the Que, and detracts from the “Innate Shi” of the United States⁹². So the picture is probably bleaker than demonstrated. China by comparison convicts 99% of those charged and in many cases simply eliminates them, in a rather dystopian “Soylent Green” like fashion in some cases⁹³.

⁸⁰ <https://www.cato.org/blog/census-finds-us-population-will-decline-without-immigration>

⁸¹ <https://clinical.diabetesjournals.org/content/22/1/1>

⁸² The industrialized genocide of infants is, infamously, rooted in Eugenics and its key adherents like Planned Parenthood founder Margaret Sanger. Estimates of the numbers of doctors, engineers, lawyers, teachers, nurses, etc. that were aborted under a poorly passed Roe v Wade (Roe is now herself anti abortion) are difficult to note. But if this had not happened, the US population would be nearly double, and the situation presented in this paper not be as dire.

Unfortunately racism is a long standing socialist programme, as it was in Nazi Germany, Zimbabwe, and many other places. Now industrialized abortion (for stem cells) is an unchecked monster ravaging the population and threatening national security. For more on the “fresh fetus parts” industry, see

<https://www.washingtonpost.com/news/wonk/wp/2015/07/17/why-planned-parenthood-wont-stop-donating-fetal-organs/> for an example of the propagandist supporting the industry.

⁸³ George Soros, Ray Dalio, Koch Brothers, Bill Gates, Jeff Bezos, Mark Zuckerberg, Bildebergers et al.

⁸⁴ See: opposition to Brexit

⁸⁵ <https://www.washingtontimes.com/news/2019/sep/26/impeach-trump-preceded-even-donald-trumps-nominati/>

⁸⁶ Such as certain people in the FBI and DOJ, and the State Department, and later the WHO and CDC.

⁸⁷ <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2020/09/an-economist-explains-what-covid-19-has-done-to-the-global-economy/>

⁸⁸ <https://www.cnn.com/2021/04/21/coronavirus-worlds-10-biggest-economies-before-covid-pandemic-vs-now.html>

⁸⁹ <https://www.motherjones.com/kevin-drum/2018/05/donald-trump-has-totally-kicked-chinas-ass-on-the-trade-deficit/>

⁹⁰ Even at 2 years in he was doing fair <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-us-canada-38663043>, despite the now defunct impeachments, however his third and fourth years were far better with two massive peace plans.

⁹¹ Some of these issues are legitimate ripples from the Civil Rights era (which was itself downstream from Jim Crow), and some are intransigent problems of the IQ and EQ deficiencies of various populations. The author believes they can be helped and positively dealt with, even within the community and not through blatantly racist policies (such as Australia’s and Canada’s infamous ‘reservation schools’). They won’t be dealt with at all via police state policy or isolationism; “sweeping a problem under the rug” has never solved any problem.

⁹²

https://www.academia.edu/49950880/CALCULATING_THE_INNATE_SHI_%E5%8B%A2_OF_COUNTRIES_USING_THE_UNITED_STATES_OF_AMERICA_AS_A_TEMPLATE_1

⁹³ Forced organ harvesting is not that far off from forced industrial cannibalism.

Figure 2.
Real Median Household Income by Race and Hispanic Origin: 1967 to 2018

Notes: The data for 2017 and beyond reflect the implementation of an updated processing system. See Appendix D for more information. The data for 2013 and beyond reflect the implementation of the redesigned income questions. See Table A-2 for historical footnotes. The data points are placed at the midpoints of the respective years. Median household income data are not available prior to 1967. For more information on recessions, see Appendix A. For more information on confidentiality protection, sampling error, nonsampling error, and definitions, see <<https://www2.census.gov/programs-surveys/cps/techdocs/cpsmar19.pdf>>.

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, Current Population Survey, 1968 to 2019 Annual Social and Economic Supplements.

Figure 1 - Median Income by Race and Ethnicity; credit: Census Bureau⁹⁴

Nevertheless, the following two figures will lead to some very important foundational discussion about the Que, and the Innate Shi, which will inform the remainder of the discussion. The above figure demonstrates the relative racial income disparities in America, and also fairly accurately the hierarchy of average IQ for each racial group (except Native Americans, which are not pictured for some unknown reason).

The graphs were produced with “millions of people” as a population designation, to provide 4 to 5 significant figures. Also, please note the curve is truncated, but this does not mean there are no people with lower or higher than 3-sigma of IQ. A sigma of 15 was used for the standard deviation of IQ⁹⁵, for all countries regardless of race, nationality, or other factors⁹⁶.

⁹⁴ <https://www.census.gov/library/visualizations/2019/demo/p60-266.html> also see: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_ethnic_groups_in_the_United_States_by_household_income Note that Indian Americans make substantially more money per household than Chinese Americans, and this might have to do with the pool of immigrants’ relative STEM involvement, entrepreneurship, government programs, time of generational expatriotship, or cultural differences (and choices of profession and region of settlement). In short the issue is divorced from the greater IQ discussion at large.

⁹⁵ [https://www.davidsongifted.org/gifted-blog/iq-and-educational-needs/#:~:text=The%20mean%2C%20or%20average%2C%20IQ,\(IQ%2085%2D115\).](https://www.davidsongifted.org/gifted-blog/iq-and-educational-needs/#:~:text=The%20mean%2C%20or%20average%2C%20IQ,(IQ%2085%2D115).)

⁹⁶ For example, roughly half of India’s population of children is exposed to fecal-oral contamination, and this is thought to have serious delitory effects upon the children’s development there. <https://www.nytimes.com/2014/07/15/world/asia/poor-sanitation-in-india-may-afflict-well-fed-children-with-malnutrition.html>

Figure 2 - China vs USA IQ distribution curves (millions vs IQ/200)

% more population China/US by IQ

Figure 3 - Visualizing the issue in terms of how many more people in China there are at each IQ level

The two graphs are shocking and yet unambiguous. In Figure 2 we learn that there are 3.3 Chinese people for every average American. This gets worse when we start to consider real intelligence (120+) when there are 6.5 Chinese people for every American with an IQ of 120. When you get to discussion of genius the problem will exceed 15x, 20x, even 30x. Another way to think about the average issue is that while an average worker in the USA has to choose to be a truck driver, nurse, or school teacher, in China they can have each one and then a little left over. So in the field of STEM, if the average IQ is around 120 and this is represented by a civil engineer, in China they can produce 3 other engineers, plus a lawyer, doctor, captain in the military,

and half a dentist. When we speak of surgeons, rocket scientists, professors, or other very high IQ positions over 130 or 140, then the problem accelerates as per Figure 3.

China vs. Europe

Europe is a bit more complicated because it is a conglomeration. Not all EU members are NATO allies. Some are within the “iron curtain”. Some former USSR states are practically NATO allies. Many have extraordinarily low IQs because of lack of STEM access or a history of being war torn (see Figure 4).

Figure 4 - Average IQ in Europe; credit: jakubmarian.com⁹⁷

Nevertheless this is a crude study at any rate, under the vein of the “innate shi” or “innate que” (counterspace of China’s innate shi minus that of other nations). So some large margin of error is to be expected.

⁹⁷ “Low average IQ of a country is indicative of low quality of education, not low “innate intelligence” of the population. IQ is measured relative to the whole population, in such a way that the average should be equal to 100 (which is why IQ tests regularly undergo a process of norming). However, since the quality of education has been improving steadily in most countries, a person scoring 100 on a modern standard IQ test would have scored around 120 on an IQ test from 1950 (this is called the [Flynn effect](https://jakubmarian.com/average-iq-in-europe-by-country-map/)). <https://jakubmarian.com/average-iq-in-europe-by-country-map/>

Figure 5 - China vs European Union IQ (again millions vs IQ/200)

% more population China/EU by IQ

Figure 6 - China vs. Europe; same story but less severe

Figure 5 looks so similar to Figure 2 that it is easy to imagine there's not a major difference. But here we reach one of the first hurdles to US retaining its 'hegemony' socioeconomic-geopolitical (SEGP): while Europe has an increased population and higher IQ average of 100... it is so hopelessly entrenched in differing ideologies, cultures, and historical allegiances, that an imperial China seems as solid as a boulder by comparison. Yet, in the later sections, when the author proposes solutions, there will be critiques to China's ascendancy as well.

China vs. Russia

Figure 7 - China vs. Russia IQ

% more population China/Russia by IQ

Figure 8 - the steepest curve yet

Looking at Russia’s curve, they are in the most precarious position of all; which isn’t historically unique for them. Caught between the power hungry and greedy Germanic EU and the power obsessed tyranny of the CCP, they have little choice but to be aggressive in the domains not controlled by the NATO powers absolutely: such as cyberspace and energy. The key to Russia’s survival will be to play two sides off one another, and await their opportunity.⁹⁸

⁹⁸ 借刀殺人 “to kill with a borrowed knife” and combined with 以逸待勞 “Wait at leisure while the enemy labors”

China vs. India

While Brazil is both smaller and weaker in average IQ⁹⁹, India seems a natural competitor to China. Unfortunately, it is still a 2nd World country just like Brazil. If it can continue to develop itself, in 30 or 40 years it could develop. Strategically it is absolutely invaluable as an encirclement partner. Historically, it is a difficult land to conquer, and very high in WQ. Militarily, however, they have been not necessarily the best American

ally in the region¹⁰⁰, owing to their displeasure with The US' strategic alliance with Pakistan. However, President Trump began speaking with India about expanding infrastructure. It wasn't so hard with the CCP's maneuvering against India via Sri Lanka^{101, 102}.

Figure 9 - India vs China IQ

% more population China/India by IQ

Figure 10 - The worst curve yet, when it comes to high IQ assets of China vs. India population.

⁹⁹ 87, with a population of 213.9 M

¹⁰⁰ https://www.faiobserver.com/region/north_america/relations-between-america-and-india/

¹⁰¹

<http://www.japantimes.co.jp/opinion/2010/06/29/commentary/world-commentary/china-and-india-competing-over-sri-lanka/>

¹⁰² <https://www.express.co.uk/news/world/1452166/india-news-china-navy-indian-ocean-conflict-sri-lanka-port-ww3-vn>

Bear in mind, the problem for India is not potential, but weakness of infrastructure. China had the power of the greatest empire in human history - post war United States - to increase it for almost 50 years, almost like an intravenous injection. They were taught finance, legal sophistication, and tons of western science and technology was acquired through theft¹⁰³ and forced IP transference¹⁰⁴, in order to access the vast markets and growth offered¹⁰⁵. It was an unholy sacrifice, based on the specious and maybe foolish supposition that capitalism and democracy being “naturally superior”¹⁰⁶ would convince the CCP to abandon its tyrannical ways and embrace freedom and totally free markets. This is now proving very false, indeed. Instead, China has accelerated kicking out westerners and even taken to openly admitting to the plan.¹⁰⁷

China vs. the World

To give the World a chance, Brazil is included while Africa, Mexico, Canada, and Australia are ignored (for simplicity). IQ’s are averaged while populations are aggregated. However, bear in mind half of Europe and Russia itself would be suspect allies. They may join a new Axis involving Italy, North Korea, China, and Iran. It is difficult to predict in the new Cold War 2/ WW3.0 environment¹⁰⁸, with the new domains of war: space and cyberspace involved in the mix (as well as lawfare). It can be assumed that despite the equally advanced intelligence and spy network of the former KGB as to its US counterparts, that a relatively similar level of infiltration and even more corruption in Russian government by CCP agents is underway. Nevertheless, we would be curious to note how the IQ asset comparison would be in a dichotomous environment. For comparison we shall also have individual overlays (except Brazil).

Figure 11 - China vs the World Allies (including Brazil), and overlays from previous figures

¹⁰³ <https://law.stanford.edu/2018/04/10/intellectual-property-china-china-stealing-american-ip/>

¹⁰⁴ <https://www.nationalreview.com/2021/06/china-is-stealing-our-technology-and-intellectual-property-congress-must-stop-it/>

¹⁰⁵ <https://money.cnn.com/2017/08/14/news/economy/trump-china-trade-intellectual-property/index.html>

¹⁰⁶ It turns out this false supposition comes from the leadership of central bankers and other NGOs, as well as the arrogance of the Nixon Administration (according to Dr. Pillsbury who was on the inside of it the entire time). Whereas in reality what gave America its advantages were cultura, strategic, geographical, and a bit of “manifest” destiny.

¹⁰⁷ https://www.theepochtimes.com/why-the-chinese-regime-wants-to-kick-out-western-journalists-now_391019.html

¹⁰⁸ Aka the Digital Cold War fought in space and cyberspace, and with hackers and AI.
<https://nationalinterest.org/feature/america-vs-russia-china-welcome-cold-war-ii-25382>

It is clear from this graph that both Brazil and India make a massive difference, while the US and EU are nearly the same, and Russia is a somewhat negligible X-factor. However, as is seen in Figure 11, China retains an important edge.

% more population China/World by IQ

Figure 12 - China vs. world, break-even point at around 109 IQ, 1 pt above Hong Kong & Singapore's values¹⁰⁹

Unfortunately, again at real intelligence, 120 IQ, we see a disparity of 1.76 Chinese people for each of the Allies'. At a genius of 140, that figure balloons to around 5.

The only good news, is if the Allies were involved in a non-nuclear Total War (NNTW) for survival of way of life, that China's population is also now aging and projected to shrink. China has, of course, thought of this, and is beginning programs of a form of genetic colonialism in its "barbarian" regions and neighbors.¹¹⁰ It started this in Tibet, but has expanded to Mongolian and steppe regions¹¹¹.

Still, while the lessons of Japan's "stagflation"¹¹²-population axial relationship¹¹³ have not fallen on deaf ears in the West, or in China it would appear, the facts of gravity are that the world population will peak at around 9 billion people¹¹⁴, and it is the 3rd and 2nd world where it will continue growing, not in China.

Mitigation of IQ Asset Que/Disadvantage

The issue of solving the deficiency or disadvantage of IQ assets is not simple. In fact it's almost certainly an insurmountable problem, pragmatically speaking. It isn't that mankind cannot unify and create the Alliance referred to before. It is that the problems of: language, politics, momentum, propensity, jealousy, distrust (including of America), and half a dozen other barriers, are not trivial. It is only made worse by one simple fact: China knows, and fears, this unity, and actively works to sow discord between allies. That's an

¹⁰⁹ Does this indicate one of China's strategic objectives in dominating those populations? How useful will an oppressed people be in supplying the "love of the People" to the hegemon's "Awesomeness" (雄壯)? We have no data to this effect, but the author would be surprised if it was 60% efficient.

¹¹⁰ 夷 (yi) or hu - traditionally anyone outside of Zhongguo 中国 (China)

¹¹¹ http://www.fao.org/ag/againfo/programmes/en/empres/news_060514b.html

¹¹² <https://www.harvardmagazine.com/2010/07/an-aftermath-to-avoid>

¹¹³ <https://swarajyamag.com/economy/why-is-japan-stagnant-for-past-30-years-answers-are-in-religion-and-culture>

¹¹⁴ <https://thenewdaily.com.au/news/2020/07/15/world-population-peak-2064/>

ancient technique, and is a complex form of Zongheng¹¹⁵ theory coming back from the Warring States to haunt the modern world. The author is a student of the theory, but in terms of statecraft it is completely impractical in modern diplomacy without being aggravating. The old problem of World War I - “entangled alliances”¹¹⁶ - is a lesson desired to only be learned once. Yet, there is nothing new to this problem in Chinese history. What’s worse is the “war hawks” (鷹派) love to “rattle the sabres” and whip up support for nationalism and war. Soviet style parades of missile and rocket launching vehicles in the capital and around the country are common¹¹⁷.

Right, so what solutions would the author offer? Thinking about the problem logically, there is a natural martial limit to what can be done. The continual employment of greater and greater powerful weapons has a practical limit both in cost and issues such as environmental destruction, etc. But the other practical issue comes from encirclement: no one can fight off enemies on all sides. This is a similar type issue to having 3, 4, even 12 or more Chinese people with your same IQ for every one of you. The only way to deal with such a situation is *leverage*. The only practical leverages in this world are: weaponry, technology, and money.¹¹⁸

Before engineering or imagining new solutions, or creative theories, we should then explore these three.¹¹⁹

1. Weaponry: the United States, Russia, and Europe have been pushing the development edge of weaponry since the end of World War II. Primarily the United States has led the way. And in almost no time, by comparison, China has managed to hack into military contractors and steal almost all of the most important battleships¹²⁰ and aircraft¹²¹, modify them, and put them into use. This is a practical application of the ancient Chinese classics, particularly one story about the collection of wisdom¹²². While the West complains, Russia flows with it and gets involved in digital warfare. At first this did not have a dampening effect on innovation in the West. But now it is becoming difficult both to compete (in practical sales and in terms of matching new weaponry). And also there is a loss of ardour for innovation, when it is known that your projects will be stolen for a fraction of the cost of hiring a large army of hackers.
2. Technology: again the innovation of the West (and Japan and South Korea) is legendary. Capitalism, democracy (or Republics), and free markets have set free mankind’s innovation. However, there is a practical cost. Hence: intellectual property rights, an extension of the liberal concept of “property rights”, a form of individual “God-given” rights¹²³. While China has plenty of property rights, they also have a long history of nationalization, often at a whim, and of frank, open theft of IP. It isn’t called theft, because the corporations are forced to “share” their IP and development. This, among other reasons, is why Google abandoned its efforts to be a supporting framework for China¹²⁴. After doing some work, it became clear that the CCP wanted

¹¹⁵ 縱橫家 Horizontal-Vertical School aka “The School of Diplomacy”; “According to the Han Feizi, a contemporary work on Legalist Philosophy, supporters of “Vertical Alliance” encourage the weak multitude to attack the one strong side whilst the Horizontal Alliance promote the one strong side attacking the weak multitude. They are all fickle and capricious, change sides frequently and are unable to decide who their master is. Both Su Qin of the Vertical Alliance clique and Zhang Yi of the Horizontal Alliance clique issue many plans and schemes that are politically subjective.”

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/School_of_Diplomacy

¹¹⁶ http://www.bellviewcoc.com/sermons-PDF/entangled_alliances.pdf

¹¹⁷ <https://www.globalsecurity.org/military/world/china/parades.htm>

¹¹⁸ In the old days religion and superstition provided a leverage over kings and nobility. But that eventually ended as the ages of the gods more and more departed, and people stopped believing they would be destroyed for violating Heaven’s Will (天意)

¹¹⁹ Without studying and examining the Innate Shi of China and the others (only USA), there’s only so much that can be said. Much will seem a bit speculative.

¹²⁰ <https://www.popularmechanics.com/military/a746/3319656/>

¹²¹ Including the \$1.5 trillion F-35

<https://www.sandboxx.us/blog/chinas-next-carrier-fighter-will-likely-be-based-on-stolen-f-35-plans/>

¹²² <https://www.gutenberg.org/files/15250/15250-h/15250-h.htm>

¹²³ See: the writings of John Locke, and of St. Thomas Aquinas.

¹²⁴ <https://www.technologyreview.com/2018/12/19/138307/how-google-took-on-china-and-lost/>

to replicate Google, modify it, and not allow them to make a real free profit in China. Also, while technology is always useful in its own domain, technology can also lead to poor sociological or environmental results. Profits may mislead thinkers and consumers into imagining something is a good, useful, or safe product. Pretty soon the technocracy is in love with a destructive technology. So that may be an important warning or note for the Allies, if they wish to use technology as leverage. Not only can it be stolen, but one can be misled this way, or that, in trying to chase the dragon.

3. Money: finance has been one of America's most powerful weapons or tools for the last 100 years. However, China has replicated the 100 years of financial sector development in only 8 years¹²⁵, and now has four of the 5 largest banks in the world.¹²⁶ Moreover, while there is (of course) corruption in Europe, America, and Russia, China has an overt tendency towards black market financial services sector. Infamously, their companies have 3 sets of accounting books.¹²⁷ This kind of flexibility, as well as their advantage of continuous inflation to avoid default of mortgages¹²⁸, and internal policy reward for all GDP, even fake GDP¹²⁹, gives China a distinct financial advantage in fiat expansion. However, at this time, very few countries trust China's currency, not even its own allies¹³⁰, who still buy US bonds and trade primarily in dollars, for stability.¹³¹

Considering these effectors and stimulators on the shi, how should the Allies, particularly the United States of America, implement its IQ assets in order to avoid 'encirclement' and being outperformed by China in a strategic battle of NNTW? The following are the areas the author feels should be primarily bolstered:

- Infrastructure
 - Replacements
 - Hardening
 - Duplications and backups
- Techno-reservations
 - Chip manufacturing
 - Energy stations and reservoirs
 - More hardening
 - Underground infrastructure and manufacturing
 - Subterranean mining at the deepest levels (with robots)
- Group IQ Redundancy
 - Think Tanks
 - Masterminds
 - Multi-board service
 - Virtual Executives and other Gig economy innovations
- Power-contracting¹³²
 - Programmers

¹²⁵ <https://carnegieendowment.org/chinafinancialmarkets/68128>

¹²⁶ <https://www.investopedia.com/articles/investing/082015/4-biggest-chinese-banks.asp>

¹²⁷ <https://foreignpolicy.com/2009/09/03/how-china-cooks-its-books/>

¹²⁸ <https://gbr.pepperdine.edu/2010/08/will-china-float-the-yuan/>

¹²⁹

<https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2018-02-01/china-s-2015-gdp-puffed-up-by-fake-economic-data-analysis-shows>

¹³⁰ <https://fee.org/articles/why-chinas-yuan-is-unlikely-to-challenge-the-dollar-anytime-soon/>

¹³¹ <https://www.afr.com/policy/foreign-affairs/we-cannot-rebuild-trust-with-china-20210715-p589xy>

¹³² Because China, and many other places, do not recognize international and US law and global ethical advance, this will probably need to be tied to digital crypto reward... a "proof of work" sort of mentality

- Engineers
- Systems Designers
- Project Managers, etc.
- Analysts
- Data Scientists
- Strong, powerful advancement in AI driven Operations Research¹³³
- Complete and total reform of primary education to be driven towards STEM and History
 - All specialisms should become intern programs in High School that lead towards technical schools, or PPSE
- AI Quantum (AIQS) supremacy¹³⁴
- Technical education programs for bingfa and zongheng specialties, particularly “Total War” etc.¹³⁵
- Keep checking back as the author is likely to think of more

While one man, with a mere IQ of 133.7 is unable to perfectly cognize solutions to this issue... if the United States and allies could at least consider this proposal and begin here, the author has no doubt a big dent could be made.

Difficulties Facing the Allies and World

In order to discuss this, it is important to stop believing the lies of the globalist position, that we “are all in this together.” That may be true from one point of view, but it is clearly a useless view in the face of practical realities, especially dealing with China, Jihadism, socialists and anarchists, and the Corporate Technocracy (an oligarchy of billionaires).¹³⁶

Once the reader is past the nonsense one can speak frankly about the difficulties and what it will take to overcome these.

The most difficult to overcome adversities to gathering IQ assets are, in no particular order, but what the author purports is a likely hierarchy (needs testing):

- Divisions or anti-cohesiveness
- Political dissipation¹³⁷
- Ubiquitous Racial Discrimination (URD¹³⁸)
- The Military Industrial Complex itself, particularly its inertia and foibles (re: contract bias and corruption)
- Cultural Egotism
- Language barriers - although less as English is pretty much the world standard
- Financial bubbles¹³⁹

¹³³ Aka Analytics, technically Op.Res. is a science and analytics uses math in that science. It’s been around for a long time

¹³⁴ See the “Asymmetric Vulnerabilities” paper by the author, pp. 18-21

¹³⁵ This is to raise public awareness and stop relying upon police and honesty and “rule of law” in an era obviously less about following the law than about the Narrative and Optics.

https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-19681-3_10

¹³⁶ The paternalism in each of these groups is only made worse with the rise of groupthink heavy maternalism, which is making generations of weak minded, pacifistic simpletons. Maternalism fails its tests at the margins of chaos, in places where ISIS rules, or fascism, or where African migrants are gangraping English women (for example).

¹³⁷ Some countries are literally ruled by 5 or 6 parties; India is such a country.

¹³⁸ Wokeness is the newest brand of racism, but there’s nothing new about regressive Leftism. It gets rebranded, but the biological wiring is the same, whatever the word-salad is. Nevertheless it is a military demoralizer

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vTRSom1Ssgs>

¹³⁹ Double Layer Economics (DLE) could do a lot to mitigate this, see the author’s new paper*

- Poor cosmology choices (which drain finances)¹⁴⁰
- Education inadequacy, slippage¹⁴¹, and substandard evolution of systems¹⁴²
- Medical inferiority¹⁴³
- Rivalry and bickering among allies, particularly around costs and jurisdiction
- Lawfare¹⁴⁴
- STEM inferiority created by design inefficiency of design¹⁴⁵
- Arrogance over present STEM superiority
- Ignorance over STEM ignorance - “you don’t know what you don’t know.”
- Vice Excess, Virtue Deficiency¹⁴⁶
- Government and banking corruption
- Nonlinear dynamics, “black swan events”¹⁴⁷, and contagion¹⁴⁸ in general.
- Chaos or what the author terms “jiggle”

In overcoming these items, there should be whole engineering and design teams, engaged by the governments, specially under the purpose of overcoming the Que. The main problem is: there’s no impetus and almost no likelihood of achieving this.

Critique of the False Awesomeness of China

One of the reasons China is so keen to accelerate their plans (and so lose the patience they long had established in this coup), is the paranoia that “things are not always what they seem.” In the classic Sun Tzu Art of War, when this seems possible, you double the marching speed to try to take the enemy unawares. Unfortunately, the pandemic has created a growing awareness of China’s agenda¹⁴⁹, and like any thief in the night exposed by sudden brightness, the CCP is panicking. Also, President Trump made them feel completely uneasy and in the jaws of the alpha male lion. The result was a reversion to some of the worst habits, policies, and a draconian crackdown on Hong Kong.¹⁵⁰ This was a very bad move, because Hong Kong was one of the best economies in the world.¹⁵¹ Another problem has been they need to out-engineer social media’s ability to spread memes and narratives which are not state approved. The world has then had a joyous bit of mirth watching a President make it illegal to compare him to Winnie the Pooh¹⁵², and increased the internet’s delight in doing exactly that.¹⁵³ This undermines the will of the CCP and its citizens, and creates a general sense that

¹⁴⁰ China is all in for PEMC, consequently their fusion reactors are winning the race, currently. At this rate they will create the world’s first Thunderbolt generator (BPT or VG). Again see “Birkeland Polyphase Superweb” pp. 28-29

¹⁴¹ Such as the United States’ since introducing “free education” in the 1930s.

¹⁴² Sticking to the RRR form of education in a modern, media-driven era.

¹⁴³ Too much to write here.

¹⁴⁴ This disadvantage is so lopsided it is not even funny. “Assym. Vuln.” pp. 26-30

¹⁴⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=L1kbriZRDvU>

¹⁴⁶ Roughly paraphrasing the Shu Jing and relying on our knowledge of Rome’s downfall: “all empires fall due to the failure of the virtue of the People alone.”

¹⁴⁷ <https://corporatefinanceinstitute.com/resources/knowledge/finance/black-swan-event/>

¹⁴⁸ <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/c/contagion.asp>

¹⁴⁹ And in no small way, brave men like General Spalding going against the grain and going on outlets like Valuetainment to spread the word.

¹⁵⁰

<https://www.forbes.com/sites/georgecalhoun/2020/07/19/the-hong-kong-crackdown-is-a-financial-disaster-for-china-is-it-time-to-fire-the-ceo/>

¹⁵¹

<https://www.breitbart.com/national-security/2020/05/22/hong-kong-economy-one-of-the-few-to-survive-pandemic-collapse-s-over-chinese-takeover/>

¹⁵² <https://alphanewsmn.com/pooh-china-ban/>

¹⁵³ <https://bitterwinter.org/xi-jinping-and-winnie-the-pooh-the-story-that-doesnt-go-away/>

the CCP is the “wizard of oz” or worse: “the emperor with no clothes.” In such a case, the Chinese people *themselves* might ask, “do we even need the Chinese Communist Party?” So while the previously quoted speech seems like rattling the sabre towards the West, it is more likely a not-so-thinly-veiled threat towards the Taiwanese republicans, and other democracy adherents within China’s mainland itself, as well as to the Muslims that might band behind Uighars and other steppe peoples to rebel against the colonialism.

Furthermore, while a large percentage of China is highly nationalistic and patriotic, and even believes the USA is a bully to China¹⁵⁴, many of the most high IQ individuals in the STEM world know differently. They see what happens to scientists from the Wuhan labs¹⁵⁵, or journalists^{156 157}, capitalists¹⁵⁸ etc. and they frequently defect or have dissident reactions. The CCP policy of welding people in their homes¹⁵⁹ or chasing them with drones¹⁶⁰ during COVID is a diametric contrast to life inside Hong Kong or the West.

Speaking of Hong Kong, as it was crushed and forced into an uneasy integration, those citizens will spread out into the mainland and take their explications of how different liberalized western living is versus coming up in a land where your family farms were stolen, fake buildings and superdams forcibly constructed to prop up GDP¹⁶¹, corruption protected while complaints punished, and finally how economic freedom and free markets really work.

Regardless of the foibles of consumerism and modern capitalism, people will not prefer poverty, tyranny and oppression, or the lack of opportunity. They will grow steadily more restless. The more the CCP tightens its grip and drains its own people (after the World pushes back), the more the Chinese People will begin to lose their ardour¹⁶².

In the United States, 9/11 united everyone into patriotic fervor¹⁶³. But as the 2003 Iraq war became more and more obviously a sham, people split back again and the country is more divided than it was since 1865.¹⁶⁴ However, it can and will obviously swing back to unity under a united threat, such as China. China knows this, and they fear the lion’s teeth all the same. While the tiger beats the lion¹⁶⁵, the lion damages the tiger also mortally and the tiger walks with a limp. When speaking of nuclear fangs, this is not a limp but missing legs and eyes. China knows this.¹⁶⁶

Also, there is a key problem for China, geographically, which has always made them leery: they are landlocked from the west, and more than half the country is not currently arable.¹⁶⁷ They can, of course, terraform and reform these regions struck by the cataclysms, but that’s costly, and they are already at 300%+ debt to GDP ratio¹⁶⁸, and living on borrowed time regarding payments, debts, derivatives, etc. Already the

¹⁵⁴ <https://foreignpolicy.com/2019/10/01/chinas-angry-young-nationalists/>

¹⁵⁵ <https://www.thesun.co.uk/news/12476233/patient-zero-scientist-wuhan-lab/>

¹⁵⁶ In China to be a journalist you have to keep up a form of licensure which is nothing more than pro-CCP propaganda. You cannot film anyone for an internet show without this “license”.

¹⁵⁷ <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-china-51486106>

¹⁵⁸

<https://www.republicworld.com/world-news/china/jack-ma-who-disappeared-along-with-4-other-billionaires-laying-low-equity-firm-ceo.html>

¹⁵⁹ <https://www.thesun.co.uk/news/10925668/coronavirus-patients-welded-homes-china/>

¹⁶⁰ <https://metro.co.uk/2020/01/31/drones-chasing-chinese-people-homes-stop-coronavirus-spreading-12162070/>

¹⁶¹ <https://www.newsweek.com/fake-cities-exploring-chinas-erie-replicas-paris-rome-and-jackson-hole-1017249>

¹⁶² 忱 (chen) - aka zeal

¹⁶³

<https://www.dallasnews.com/opinion/commentary/2016/09/09/as-9-11-would-prove-we-americans-just-don-t-do-unity-very-well/>

¹⁶⁴ <https://thehill.com/hilltv/what-americas-thinking/409718-analyst-says-the-us-is-the-most-divided-since-the-civil-war>

¹⁶⁵ https://military.wikia.org/wiki/Atlas_the_Barbarian_lion_versus_the_Bengal_tiger_of_Simla

¹⁶⁶ “Sun Tzu said: In the practical art of war, the best thing of all is to take the enemy’s country whole and intact; to shatter and destroy it is not so good. So, too, it is better to recapture an army entire than to destroy it, to capture a regiment, a detachment or a company entire than to destroy them.” ~ Sun Tzu <http://classics.mit.edu/Tzu/artwar.html>

¹⁶⁷ <https://www.bloomberg.com/graphics/2017-feeding-china/>

¹⁶⁸ <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-china-economy-debt-idUSKCN1UD0KD>

buildings begin to literally fall over¹⁶⁹, though they are mere years old. The veneer wears thin and frail. The tiger begins to look like a paper tiger. Instead of a “tiger claw” we are seeing a “cat’s paw”.¹⁷⁰

Figure 13 - Jet Li tells it like it is in “Fearless”

Finally, while China’s IQ advantage is *probably* insurmountable, it already began to weaken itself - nature takes its course. The smartest and wisest genes leave China and strike out to Africa, Europe, Oceania, and America of course, and will take their know-how with them, and become less and less available to the will of the CCP and their leverage. This is good for the world and for Chinese people. But it leaves China already becoming overweight, and aging, and hollowed out - so to speak - to return back to a worker force society. They want to rapidly enter a services society, but it is not the habit of the people themselves. Right now the habit is to wait on the CCP to fix anything wrong¹⁷¹. There is a Chinese story, about Huangdi¹⁷², which lays out the issue thoroughly: in the end, it was Huangdi’s desire to micro-manage Tian-xia¹⁷³ that led to his illness. It was his egolessness that led to all under Heaven becoming his and flourishing.¹⁷⁴ This is a PEMC concept as well.¹⁷⁵

There is also one unavoidable fact about the paper tiger of China: it has never been a world superpower and gone to war outside itself in the last 500 years¹⁷⁶. Its military can run games and they can steal all of the US Military manuals it wants, and analyze the data of US war battles, but take it from the author who is a Chinese martial artist and western pugilist... all plans go out the window once you’ve been punched in the face by an actual fighter.

China has too much to lose to fight that way, and now too much to lose to fight in all other ways, unless it sticks to the asymmetric battle plan. No matter if you control the world for a bit, or people’s wills for a while, you cannot be a literal hegemon without the blood and guts of symmetric warfare. There are no instances the author can think of, of permanent victory without it. When and if China decides to play that hand, the real might of the Allies will come out, which is hidden in dusty battle plans, boxes, and secret storage facilities in the Rockies. Therefore, the Allies have **time** to develop their IQ, WQ, and hopefully EQ; to reduce the Que, and balance things out in the favor of democracy, free markets of ideas, etc.

Like “stolen valor”¹⁷⁷ the only thing more wretched and pathetic than martial cowardice, is fake Awesomeness. No matter what, a bully is never considered awesome, and cannot win the “Love of the People.” If America has lost this recently, that’s nature’s course. But it can be found again in patriotic fervor when the American immune system sheds itself of the socialist (Germano-Russian) pathogenic strain of thought which saps the will, and makes the mind lazy and cowardly. However, until that happens, the alliance may be hindered, and it is advisable to not underestimate the danger of an adversary like China.

¹⁶⁹

<https://www.dailymail.co.uk/news/article-1196064/Tumbling-tower-China-Amazing-pictures-13-storey-block-flats-toppled-over.html>

¹⁷⁰ 虎爪 hu zhua vs 猫掌 mao zhang https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oLrNu_w--xw (2:47)

¹⁷¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IAoTBVTTO8>

¹⁷² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Yellow_Emperor

¹⁷³ 天下; lit: “all under Heaven”; ie the empire.

¹⁷⁴ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Huangdi>

¹⁷⁵ Pushing electrons to make electricity is not the pattern we see in the cosmos!

¹⁷⁶ Saving perhaps Tibet, if one can call a coup like that a war. They essentially pushed over old men and children who had no defenses at all. It cannot be said to be a military victory.

¹⁷⁷ <http://www.stolenvalor.com/>

Conclusion

The Innate Shi of China is strongly bolstered by the advantage of IQ assets. However, the World has developments it can do to offset this. Even if China is aware of this advantage, or intuitively cognizant, the fact is that not all art of war factors lie in China's favor. It will, therefore, probably continue along its present course, and extend WW3.0 in order to utilize this advantage, and avoid real conflict. However, this advantage will begin to dissipate over 30 years of time, as well. However, as a cautionary tale, so will (and rapidly) the US and EU's advantages.

Therefore rapid development of key allies in Brazil and India is encouraged, as well as fixing the problems with totally subverted allies such as Australia, Italy, Russia, Mexico, Canada, etc. Without this, the free market conditions necessary for the next level of human expansion and development will be delayed, including any possibility of the Double Layer Economics (to save Globalism and promote sovereign peace and independence.). The US Congress and EU members are encouraged to immediately seek to implement the ideas contained, and "bide for time" to make oneself stronger (or strong again). Patience, and withdrawal, are the most complete pathways forward, at this time. The path of developing "in the dark" is advised, as opposed to the current US policy of frightening the world with terrible power and announcing ever newer technologies and abilities.

References

1. "IQ, EQ, ... but what about WQ?", Wordpress, M. Bassous, 2013, <https://mbassous.wordpress.com/category/wisdom-quotient/>
2. "Fauci, Rand Paul clash over 'gain-of-function' research at Wuhan lab in China," New York Post, M. Moore, 2021, <https://nypost.com/2021/07/20/fauci-sen-paul-clash-over-gain-of-function-research-at-wuhan-lab-in-china/>
3. "Fight Over Covid's Origins Renews Debate on Risks of Lab Work." New York Times, C. Zimmer and J. Gorman, 2021, <https://www.nytimes.com/2021/06/20/science/covid-lab-leak-wuhan.html>
4. "COVID-19 misinformation by China," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/COVID-19_misinformation_by_China
5. "China's Intelligence Networks in United States Include 25,000 Spies," The Washington Free Beacon, B. Gertz, 2017, <https://freebeacon.com/national-security/chinas-spy-network-united-states-includes-25000-intelligence-officers/>
6. "Racing to Success, UK Celebrates China Tie," Univ of Kentucky PR & Marketing, E. Holaday, 2010, <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1pVbfeTOjkHU3cakNF86mRdR7bC7kmlYs/view>
7. "Belt and Road Initiative," Council on Foreign Relations, J. Lew et al., 2021, <https://www.cfr.org/belt-and-road-initiative>
8. "Neo-Colonialism in Africa? The Chinese Belt and Road Initiative," Leeds Finsights (Leeds Student Financial Publication,) B. Harris, 2020, <https://www.leedsfinsights.com/post/neo-colonialism-in-africa-the-chinese-belt-and-road-initiative>
9. "Belt and Road: colonialism with Chinese characteristics," The Interpreter- Lowy Institute, A. Kleven, 2019, <https://www.lowyinstitute.org/the-interpreter/belt-and-road-colonialism-chinese-characteristics>
10. "China's Belt and Road Initiative: Debt Colonialism or Genuine Investment?" Citizen Truth, Y. Rasidi, 2018, <https://citizentruth.org/china-africa-belt-and-road-initiative/>
11. "100 Year Marathon," Dr. Pillsbury, 2014
12. "Stealth War: How China Took Over While America's Elite Slept," R. Spalding, 2018 <https://www.stealth-war.org/>
13. "Marshall Plan," Britannica, Encyclopedia Britannica, The Editors of Encyclopedia, 2020, <https://www.britannica.com/event/Marshall-Plan>
14. "U.S. impending war with China," The Washington Times, B. Fein, 2017, <https://www.washingtontimes.com/news/2017/jan/27/us-impending-war-china/>
15. "Xi Jinping undertakes fresh round of brutal purge in China," The Times of India, Ani, 2020, <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/world/china/xi-jinping-undertakes-fresh-round-of-brutal-purge-in-china/articleshow/77943864.cms>

16. "China's sudden rush to crush Hong Kong's freedom," New York Post, Post Editorial Board, 2020, <https://nypost.com/2020/05/21/chinas-sudden-rush-to-crush-hong-kongs-freedom/>
17. "2021 Index of Economic Freedom," Heritage, 2021, <https://www.heritage.org/index/ranking>
18. "Xi Jinping said other countries will 'crack their heads and spill blood' if they come after China, a stark warning to mark 100 years of the Communist Party, Insider, S. Baker and C. Teh, 2021, <https://www.businessinsider.com/xi-countries-opposing-china-crack-heads-spill-blood-2021-7>
19. "China Slams G-7 Statement Criticizing Human Rights Record, Vox , VOA News, 2021, <https://www.voanews.com/east-asia-pacific/china-slams-g-7-statement-criticizing-human-rights-record>
20. "Socialism: The Failed Idea That Never Dies," Forbes, R Zitelmann, 2020, <https://www.forbes.com/sites/rainerzitelmann/2020/03/16/socialism-the-failed-idea-that-never-dies/>
21. "Why do socialists always blame someone else?" Northeast Shooters, 2005, <https://www.northeastshooters.com/xen/threads/why-do-socialists-always-blame-someone-else.3480/>
22. "East German kids were 'taught to lie.' Then the system came crashing down overnight," CNN World, S. McKenzie and N. Schmidt, 2019, <https://www.cnn.com/2019/11/09/europe/berlin-wall-30-years-schools-grm-intl/index.html>
23. "Black Lives Matter," BLM, 2013, <https://blacklivesmatter.com/about/>
24. "These 18 Corporations Gave Money to Radical Black Lives Matter Group," The Daily Signal, F. Lucas, 2020, <https://www.dailysignal.com/2020/07/07/these-18-corporations-gave-money-to-black-lives-matter-group/>
25. "Big Lie," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Big_lie
26. "VIDEO: James O'Keefe Breaks Down BIG WIN Against The New York Times in Veritas Defamation Lawsuit – Explains Massive Media Ramifications for the Future," Project Veritas, 2021, <https://www.projectveritas.com/news/video-james-okeefe-breaks-down-big-win-against-the-new-york-times-in-veritas/>
27. "Project Veritas and Their Undercover Sting Operation Against The Washington Post," The Data Lounge, 2018, <https://www.datalounge.com/thread/20086703-project-veritas-and-their-undercover-sting-operation-against-the-washington-post>
28. "China's 50 Cent Army: Infuriating Trolls, Liars, and Hackers," Economic Independence, 2020, <https://economicindependencefromchina.com/chinas-50-cent-army/>
29. "Revealing the Operations of China's Official Troll Army System," The Epoch Times, N. Hao, 2020, https://www.theepochtimes.com/revealing-the-operations-of-chinas-official-troll-army-system_3311813.html
30. "Defining Asymmetric Warfare," The Land Warfare Papers, D. L. Buffaloe, 2006, <https://www.ausa.org/sites/default/files/LWP-58-Defining-Asymmetric-Warfare.pdf>
31. "Unrestricted Warfare," Beijing: PLA Literature and Arts Publishing House, Qiao Liang and Wang Xiangsui 1999, <https://www.oodaloo.com/documents/unrestricted.pdf>
32. "Total War," - Oxford Companion to Military History, Oxford University Press, 2001, <https://www.cc.gatech.edu/~tpilsch/INTA4803TP/Articles/Total%20War-definition&discussion.pdf>
33. "'How China Is Colonizing Africa Using Trade, Aid, and Debt-Trap Diplomacy,'" Education For Liberation, <https://www.panafricanalliance.com/china-africa-colonialism/>
34. "China In Africa: The New Colonialism," US Government Publishing House, Washington, 2018, <https://docs.house.gov/meetings/FA/FA16/20180307/106963/HHRG-115-FA16-Transcript-20180307.pdf>
35. "The ABC's China Interference Investigations," Australian Institute of International Affairs, Dr. A. Chubb, 2019, <https://www.internationalaffairs.org.au/australianoutlook/abc-china-interference-investigations/>
36. "How China Interferes in Australia and How Democracies Can Push Back," Foreign Affairs, J.Garnaut, 2018, <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/articles/china/2018-03-09/how-china-interferes-australia>
37. "China's Air Incursions Into Taiwan's ADIZ Focus on 'Anti-Access' and Maritime Deterrence," The Diplomat, O.Pekka Suorsa and A. Ang U-Jin, 2021, <https://thediplomat.com/2021/07/chinas-air-incursions-into-taiwans-adiz-focus-on-anti-access-and-maritime-deterrence/>
38. "2020–2021 China–India skirmishes," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2020%E2%80%932021_China%E2%80%93India_skirmishes
39. "China's 'New Silk Road' brings great promise to eastern Europe," Deutsche Welle: Made for Minds, A.Vangeli, 2016, <https://www.dw.com/en/chinas-new-silk-road-brings-great-promise-to-eastern-europe/a-36271021>
40. "The Belt and Road in Europe: 5 Years Later," The Diplomat, N. Rolland, 2018, <https://thediplomat.com/2018/08/the-belt-and-road-in-europe-5-years-later/>
41. "The myth of the Belt and Road in Central and Eastern Europe," Blog: Panda Paw Dragon Claw, T. Matura, 2019, <https://pandapawdragonclaw.blog/2019/05/05/the-myth-of-the-belt-and-road-in-central-and-eastern-europe/>
42. "China's Stakes in Venezuela are Too High to be Ignored," Columbia/Sipa : Journal of International Affairs, I. Patrick and L. Wosgrau Padilha, 2021, <https://jia.sipa.columbia.edu/online-articles/chinas-stakes-venezuela-are-too-high-be-ignored>
43. "China's Engagement with Latin America and the Caribbean," U.S.-China Economic and Security Review Commission, K.Koleski and A. Blivas, 2018,

https://www.uscc.gov/sites/default/files/Research/China%27s%20Engagement%20with%20Latin%20America%20and%20the%20Caribbean_.pdf

44. "Italy Has Learned a Tough Lesson on China," Foreign Policy, L. Meacci, 2021, <https://foreignpolicy.com/2021/06/24/italy-china-policy-belt-road/>
45. "Italy: A New Silk Road Between Italy and China – the Belt and Road Initiative," The Library of Congress Blog, E. Hofverberg, 2020, <https://blogs.loc.gov/law/2020/05/italy-a-new-silk-road-between-italy-and-china-the-belt-and-road-initiative/>
46. "China in Sri Lanka: The Colombo Port Conundrum: Sri Lanka's Parliament postponed discussion of a bill regarding Colombo Port City, but it is expected to pass.," The Diplomat, R. Pillai Rajagopalan, 2021, <https://thediplomat.com/2021/05/china-in-sri-lanka-the-colombo-port-conundrum/>
47. "How and Why China is Building Islands in the South China Sea," Newsweek, E. Ross, 2017, <https://www.newsweek.com/china-south-china-sea-islands-build-military-territory-expand-575161>
48. "China's Maritime Militia Vessels May Be Military Objectives During Armed Conflict," The Diplomat, J. Kraska, 2020, <https://thediplomat.com/2020/07/chinas-maritime-militia-vessels-may-be-military-objectives-during-armed-conflict/>
49. "Philippines warns China of 'unwanted hostilities' in sea dispute: Duterte's top legal counsel warns China's 'present territorial incursions' is an 'unwelcome stain' in closer ties between Manila and Beijing." Aljazeera, 2021, <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2021/4/6/philippine-warns-china-of-unwanted-hostilities-over-sea-dispute>
50. "Taking China's pulse." The Harvard Gazette, D. Harsha, 2020, <https://news.harvard.edu/gazette/story/2020/07/long-term-survey-reveals-chinese-government-satisfaction/>
51. "When the US and China Were Allies," The Diplomat, S. Tiezzi, 2015, <https://thediplomat.com/2015/08/when-the-us-and-china-were-allies/>
52. "Richard Nixon's Opening to China and Closing the Gold Window," History Today, I. Morgan, 2018, <https://www.historytoday.com/history-matters/richard-nixons-opening-china-and-closing-gold-window>
53. "Rupture between USSR and China grows worse: July 14, 1963," History, History.com Editors, 2009, <https://www.history.com/this-day-in-history/rupture-between-ussr-and-china-grows-worse>
54. "一山不容二虎," Wiktionary <https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/%E4%B8%80%E5%B1%B1%E4%B8%8D%E5%AE%B9%E4%BA%8C%E8%99%8E>
55. "Thirty-Six Stratagems," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Thirty-Six_Stratagems
56. "Understanding China's Digital Yuan," Investopedia Market News, R. Sharma, 2020, <https://www.investopedia.com/understanding-chinas-digital-yuan-5090699>
57. "Treasury Sanctions Russia with Sweeping New Sanctions Authority, US Department of the Treasury Press Release, 2021, <https://home.treasury.gov/news/press-releases/jy0127>
58. "U.S. Sanctions on Russia: An Overview, Congressional Research Service Reports, 2021, <https://fas.org/sgp/crs/row/IF10779.pdf>
59. "Soviets declare war on Japan; invade Manchuria: August 8, 1945," History, History.com Editors, 2010, <https://www.history.com/this-day-in-history/soviets-declare-war-on-japan-invade-manchuria>
60. "Russia and China Launch New Gas Pipeline, Build First Bridge in Bid to Transform East," Newsweek World, T. O'Connor, 2019, <https://www.newsweek.com/russia-china-gas-pipeline-first-bridge-1475067>
61. "How the Yuan Could Become a Global Currency," The Balance, K. Amadeo, 2021, <https://www.thebalance.com/yuan-reserve-currency-to-global-currency-3970465>
62. "Don't Discount the Dollar Yet, Foreign Policy, J.W. Sullivan, 2020, <https://foreignpolicy.com/2020/08/21/dollar-global-reserve-currency-yuan-china/>
63. "Census Finds U.S. Population Will Decline Without Immigration," Cato Institute, D. J. Bier, 2020, <https://www.cato.org/blog/census-finds-us-population-will-decline-without-immigration>
64. "Obesity in America: It's Getting Worse," American Diabetes Association, J. B. Marks, 2004, <https://clinical.diabetesjournals.org/content/22/1/1>
65. "Why drug companies need human tissue—especially liver," The Washington Post, D. Paquette, 2015, <https://www.washingtonpost.com/news/wonk/wp/2015/07/17/why-planned-parenthood-wont-stop-donating-fetal-organs/>
66. "'Impeach Trump' even preceded Donald Trump's nomination," The Washington Times, C.K. Chumley, 2019, <https://www.washingtontimes.com/news/2019/sep/26/impeach-trump-preceded-even-donald-trumps-nominati/>
67. "World Vs Virus podcast: An economist explains what COVID-19 has done to the global economy," World Economic Forum, N. Behraves, 2020, <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2020/09/an-economist-explains-what-covid-19-has-done-to-the-global-economy/>
68. Here are the 10 biggest economies in the world — before the pandemic vs. now," CNBC, Y Nee Lee, 2021, <https://www.cnbc.com/2021/04/21/coronavirus-worlds-10-biggest-economies-before-covid-pandemic-vs-now.html>

69. "Donald Trump Has Totally Kicked China's Ass on the Trade Deficit," Mother Jones, K. Drum, 2018, <https://www.motherjones.com/kevin-drum/2018/05/donald-trump-has-totally-kicked-chinas-ass-on-the-trade-deficit>
70. "Trump tracker: How his first two years have gone - in eight graphics," BBC News, M. Hills, 2019, <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-us-canada-38663043>
71. "Calculating The Innate "SHI" 勢 Of Countries Using THE United States Of America As a Template," Academia, Sf. A. R. Careaga, 2019, https://www.academia.edu/49950880/CALCULATING_THE_INNATE_SHI_%E5%8B%A2_OF_COUNTRIES_USING_THE_UNITED_STATES_OF_AMERICA_AS_A_TEMPLATE_1
72. "Income and Poverty in the United States: 2018-Current Population Reports," United States Census Bureau, J. Semega et al., 2019, <https://www.census.gov/library/visualizations/2019/demo/p60-266.html>
73. "List of ethnic groups in the United States by household income," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_ethnic_groups_in_the_United_States_by_household_income
74. "IQ and Educational Needs," Davidson Institute Blog, 2015, <https://www.davidsongifted.org/gifted-blog/iq-and-educational-needs/>
75. "Poor Sanitation in India May Afflict Well-Fed Children With Malnutrition," The New York Times, G. Harris, 2014, <https://www.nytimes.com/2014/07/15/world/asia/poor-sanitation-in-india-may-afflict-well-fed-children-with-malnutrition.html>
76. "Flynn Effect," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Flynn_effect
77. "Average IQ in Europe by country (map)," JacobMarian.com., J. Marian, <https://jakubmarian.com/average-iq-in-europe-by-country-map/>
78. 借刀殺人 "to kill with a borrowed knife" and combined with 以逸待勞 "Wait at leisure while the enemy labors"
79. "Relations Between America and India," Fair Observer, A. Singh, 2012, https://www.fairobserver.com/region/north_america/relations-between-america-and-india/
80. "China and India competing over Sri Lanka," The Japan Times, H.V. Pant, <https://www.japantimes.co.jp/opinion/2010/06/29/commentary/world-commentary/china-and-india-competing-over-sri-lanka/>
81. "Indian Navy on high alert for new China threat – Beijing military take over Sri Lankan port," Express UK News, T. McNulty, 2021, <https://www.express.co.uk/news/world/1452166/india-news-china-navy-indian-ocean-conflict-sri-lanka-port-ww3-v>
82. "Intellectual Property and China: Is China Stealing American IP?," Stanford Law School Blog, P. Goldstein, 2018, <https://law.stanford.edu/2018/04/10/intellectual-property-china-china-stealing-american-ip/>
83. "China Is Stealing Our Technology and Intellectual Property. Congress Must Stop It," National Review: World, D. Blumenthal and L. Zhang, 2021, <https://www.nationalreview.com/2021/06/china-is-stealing-our-technology-and-intellectual-property-congress-must-stop-it/>
84. "How China squeezes tech secrets from U.S. companies," CNN Business, J. Mullen, 2017, <https://money.cnn.com/2017/08/14/news/economy/trump-china-trade-intellectual-property/index.html>
85. "Why the Chinese Regime Wants to Kick Out Western Journalists Now," The Epoch Times, D. Zhang, 2013, https://www.theepochtimes.com/why-the-chinese-regime-wants-to-kick-out-western-journalists-now_391019.html
86. "America vs. Russia and China: Welcome to Cold War II," The National Interest, M. Lind, 2018, <https://nationalinterest.org/feature/america-vs-russia-china-welcome-cold-war-ii-25382>
87. "Mongolia Preparedness in Event of PPR Incursion from China," Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations, 2014, http://www.fao.org/ag/againfo/programmes/en/empres/news_060514b.html
88. "An Aftermath to Avoid," Harvard Magazine, 2010, <https://www.harvardmagazine.com/2010/07/an-aftermath-to-avoid>
89. "Why Japan Has Been Stagnant For 30 Years: Answers Are in Religion And Culture," Swarajya: Economy, Anand, 2017, <https://swarajyamag.com/economy/why-is-japan-stagnant-for-past-30-years-answers-are-in-religion-and-culture>
90. "World population to peak at 9.7 billion by 2064, before falling," The NewDaily, N. Marshall, 2020, <https://thenewdaily.com.au/news/2020/07/15/world-population-peak-2064/>
91. "School of Diplomacy," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/School_of_Diplomacy
92. "Entangled Alliances," Sermons from Bellviewcoc.com, http://www.bellviewcoc.com/sermons-PDF/entangled_alliances.pdf
93. "Chinese Military Parades," Global Security.org: Military, <https://www.globalsecurity.org/military/world/china/parades.htm>
94. "How China Steals U.S. Military Secrets," Popular Mechanics, S. Cooper, 2009, <https://www.popularmechanics.com/military/a746/3319656/>
95. "China's Next Carrier Fighter Will Likely Be Based On Stolen F-35 Plans," Sandbox: US blog, A. Hollings, 2020, <https://www.sandboxx.us/blog/chinas-next-carrier-fighter-will-likely-be-based-on-stolen-f-35-plans/>

96. "Myths and Legends of China," The Project Gutenberg, E. T. C. Werner, 2005, <https://www.gutenberg.org/files/15250/15250-h/15250-h.htm>
97. See: the writings of John Locke, and of St. Thomas Aquinas.
98. "How Google took on China—and lost," MIT Technology Review, M. Sheehan, 2018, <https://www.technologyreview.com/2018/12/19/138307/how-google-took-on-china-and-lost/>
99. "China and the History of U.S. Growth Models," Carnegie Endowment for International Peace, M. Pettis, 2017, <https://carnegieendowment.org/chinafinancialmarkets/68128>
100. "The 4 Biggest Chinese Banks," Investopedia, T. Segal, 2021, <https://www.investopedia.com/articles/investing/082015/4-biggest-chinese-banks.asp>
101. "How China Cooks Its Books," Foreign Policy: Dispatch, J. Callinoff, 2009, <https://foreignpolicy.com/2009/09/03/how-china-cooks-its-books/>
102. "Will China Float the Yuan?" Graziadio/Pepperdine Business Review Volume 8 , P.J. Crawford, PhD and T.Young, PhD, 2005, <https://gbr.pepperdine.edu/2010/08/will-china-float-the-yuan/>
103. <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2018-02-01/china-s-2015-gdp-puffed-up-by-fake-economic-data-an-alysis-shows> (need to use different computer- will not allow me w/out subscrip)
104. "Why China's Yuan Is Unlikely to Challenge the Dollar Anytime Soon," Foundation for Economic Education, C. Testoni Cardozo, 2018, <https://fee.org/articles/why-chinas-yuan-is-unlikely-to-challenge-the-dollar-anytime-soon/>
105. "We cannot rebuild trust with China," Financial Review:Opinion, T. Switzer, 2021, <https://www.afr.com/policy/foreign-affairs/we-cannot-rebuild-trust-with-china-20210715-p589xy>
106. "Asymmetric Vulnerabilities" paper by the author, pp. 18-21
107. "Narratives and Optics: Communication Dynamics Political Leaders Face Today," Springer, W. Howe and J.C. Santora, 2019, https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-19681-3_10
108. "Birkeland Polyphase Superweb" pp. 28-29, https://www.academia.edu/38560727/Birkeland_Polyphase_Superweb_A_Proposition_for_the_Future_Betterment_of_Mankind_global_defense_interconnection_and_unlimited_power
109. "Black Swan Event," Corporate Finance Institute,
110. "Contagion," Investopedia, A. Ganti, 2021, <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/c/contagion.asp>
- 111."The Hong Kong Crackdown Is A Financial Disaster For China: Is It Time To Fire The CEO?" Forbes, G. Calhoun, 2020, <https://www.forbes.com/sites/georgecalhoun/2020/07/19/the-hong-kong-crackdown-is-a-financial-disaster-for-china-is-it-time-to-fire-the-ceo/>
112. "Hong Kong Economy, One of the Few to Survive Pandemic, Collapses over Chinese Takeover," Breitbart, J. Hayward, 2020, <https://www.breitbart.com/national-security/2020/05/22/hong-kong-economy-one-of-the-few-to-survive-pandemic-collapses-over-chinese-takeover/>
113. "Winnie The Pooh Is Banned In China— Here's Why," Alpha News,K. Hooten, 2020, <https://alphanewsmn.com/pooh-china-ban/>
114. "Xi Jinping and Winnie the Pooh: The Story That Doesn't Go Away," Bitter Winter, M. Introvigne, 2019, <https://bitterwinter.org/xi-jinping-and-winnie-the-pooh-the-story-that-doesnt-go-away/>
115. "China's Youth Are Trapped in the Cult of Nationalism," Foreign Policy, V. Xiuzhong Xu, 2019, <https://foreignpolicy.com/2019/10/01/chinas-angry-young-nationalists/>
116. "WHERE IS SHE? Hunt for 'Patient Zero' scientist who 'disappeared' from Wuhan lab after coronavirus outbreak," The Sun: World News, M. Hodge, 2020, <https://www.thesun.co.uk/news/12476233/patient-zero-scientist-wuhan-lab/>
117. "Coronavirus: Why have two reporters in Wuhan disappeared?" BBC News, 2020, <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-china-51486106>
118. "Jack Ma Who Disappeared Along With 4 Other Billionaires 'laying Low': Equity Firm CEO," Republic World.com., Z. Majeed, 2021, <https://www.republicworld.com/world-news/china/jack-ma-who-disappeared-along-with-4-other-billionaires-laying-low-equity-firm-ceo.html>
119. "SEALED IN VIRUS TOMB Coronavirus patients Welded into homes in China as death toll spirals to 813," The Sun, N. Stow, 2020, <https://www.thesun.co.uk/news/10925668/coronavirus-patients-welded-homes-china/>
120. <https://metro.co.uk/2020/01/31/drones-chasing-chinese-people-homes-stop-coronavirus-spreading-12162070/>
121. "Drones are chasing Chinese people into their homes to stop the coronavirus spreading," J. Hamill, Jan 31, 2020 <https://metro.co.uk/2020/01/31/drones-chasing-chinese-people-homes-stop-coronavirus-spreading-12162070/>
122. "Inside China's Incredible 'Fake Cities': Why Even Xi Jinping Couldn't Stop Replicas of the World's Greatest Landmarks," Newsweek: World, C. Zhao, 2018, <https://www.newsweek.com/fake-cities-exploring-chinas-eerie-replicas-paris-rome-and-jackson-hole-1017249>
123. "As 9/11 would prove, we Americans just don't do unity very well," The Dallas Morning News: Opinion, M. Hashimoto, 2016,

- <https://www.dallasnews.com/opinion/commentary/2016/09/09/as-9-11-would-prove-we-americans-just-don-t-do-un-ity-very-well/>
124. "Analyst says US is most divided since Civil War," The Hill, B.Schneider, 2018, <https://thehill.com/hilltv/what-americas-thinking/409718-analyst-says-the-us-is-the-most-divided-since-the-civil-war>
 125. "Atlas the Barbary lion versus the Bengal tiger of Simla," Military wikia.org., https://military.wikia.org/wiki/Atlas_the_Barbary_lion_versus_the_Bengal_tiger_of_Simla
 126. "The Art of War," The Internet Classics Archive , Sun Tzu, <http://classics.mit.edu/Tzu/artwar.html>
 127. "Farming the World: China's Epic Race to Avoid a Food Crisis" <https://www.bloomberg.com/graphics/2017-feeding-china/>
 128. "China's debt tops 300% of GDP, now 15% of global total: IIF," Reuters, By Reuters Staff, 2019, <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-china-economy-debt-idUSKCN1UD0KD>
 129. "Tumbling tower of China: Amazing pictures of 13-storey block of flats that toppled over," Daily Mail, By Daily Mail Reporter, 2009, <https://www.dailymail.co.uk/news/article-1196064/Tumbling-tower-China-Amazing-pictures-13-storey-block-flats-to-ppled-over.html>
 130. "Yellow Emperor," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Yellow_Emperor
 131. "Huangdi: Chinese mythological emperor," Encyclopedia Britannica, By Editors of Encyclopedia, <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Huangdi>
 132. "Stolen Valor: Heroes and Patriots or are they," Stolen Valor.com. <http://www.stolenvalor.com/>